

Unfolding relationship of Word discourse & Time Factor through ‘Word Knowledge Acquisition’

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Abstract: ‘Word sense disambiguation’ is a state-of-art solution attempts to determine the sense of a word from contextual features in a running text. Major barriers to building a high-performing word sense disambiguation system include the difficulty of labeling data for this task and of predicting fine-grained sense distinctions. However, the real word knowledge of a word is attached to its discourse factor and the same further dynamically linked with ‘Time factor’. Again, discourse analysis is a field of study, in particular the examination of language use by members of a speech community. It is a subfield of pragmatics involves the analysis of both language form and language function. Authors such as Chafe, who claimed that discourse is better, studied as a process unfolding through time, is taken seriously into account. For this purpose, in this paper we have tried unfolds the ‘total word knowledge’ through the ‘knowledge discourse structure’, where ‘time’, the ultimate end knowledge and as the focal point of any word transfers communicator to communicant through ‘atomic components of thought’. For this here, we catalyze the Hindu Mythological term ‘Radha’ as the instance of analysis and try to unfold its decoding discourse of thought, its conservation and transformation.

Key Words: Word meaning, Word Knowledge, Radha, Krishna, Discourse, Rasa, Raasa, Time, Love, Aesthetics, Thought

1. Introduction:

Discourse refers to the way that conversations flow, i.e. to analyze the use of spoken or written language in a social context. It refers to a unit of language longer than a single sentence. “It can involve matters like context, background information or knowledge shared between a speaker and hearer,” (Bloor and Bloor 2013). Numerous studies have attempted to specify the meaning and function of language within the premises of Discourse Analysis (DA), e.g. Austin’s (1962) Speech Act Theory; Hymes’s (1974) *Ethnography of Communication*; Crystal’s (1985) *Deixis*; Fairclough’s (1992) ‘Three-dimensional framework; Schiffrin’s (1994) Cooperative principle; Fraser’s (1999) Discourse markers; Blommaert & Bulcaen’s (2000) *Critical Discourse Analysis*; Chilton’s (2014) ‘the use of language’; Innocent Chiluwa’s (2019) *Discourse Analysis and Conflict Studies*.

However, in the process of communication, the research gap is visible that nowhere it is described where the knowledge of a communication is present. Is it in a word or whole of the communication? If it is in the entire communication, then, how the minimum unity of the language ‘the Word’ can be separated from the analysis? Therefore here is to find out the focal point of word-knowledge, the primary communication entity of a language that has been transferred from communicator to Communicant. To understand the word knowledge beyond its semantics, i.e. more micro exploration of real world knowledge within the word itself, we try to explore the interaction between lexical semantics and pragmatics of the word. As our way, the pragmatic inference is open-ended and involves arbitrary real-world knowledge. We demonstrate we have tried here to showcase our word knowledge interpretation module. As the model’s interaction allows us to achieve a more refined interpretation of words in a discourse context than either the lexicon or pragmatics could do on their own. And the refined interpretation can be expressively understood through the ‘Atomic components of thought’ where the discourse of word knowledge transfers to wave of time.

2. Atomic Components of thought:

Thought is nothing but the representation of knowledge. “All things would be visibly connected if one could discover at a single glance and in its totality the tracings of an Ariadne’s thread leading thought into its own labyrinth”.¹ Every thought it may express or not having four primary internal components. These are (I) Goal (II) Mood or stage of concuss (III) Thought Direction (positive or negative) In every point, even if before the expression of thought by communicant there is a goal being fixed as a goal has the character of an intention. At the time of communication a desire of expression can be considered as the initial goal for germination of thought which can be said as the power house of the thought which receives the central keys. A mood is being created to activate that goal. If the mood not becomes effective or tends to relative less by the effective of communicator or any other things then the thought is not goes in effective direction.

3. The word knowledge Diagram:

Jerry R. Hobbs (1987) also tried to make a relationship between the World Knowledge and Word Meaning. However in our way, the real world word knowledge both connotative and denotative can be explored in a top-down approach starting from the discourse ring the inner ring of Pragmatics itself till to reach the ultimate time factor. The whole sphere of the discourse of a word is a systematic unfolding the sphere of the word knowledge after entering the focal point of word knowledge, or the ultimate time factor. And the same we have already discussed in our previous papers. However, for better presentation, here we further put the same to establish its relationship with thought and time wave.

The decisive meanings of any word are not static but are dynamic and are very much revolve around the context of the text. Johnson Laird (1976), Smith and Medin (1981), Barbara C. Malt (1998), R.G. Fukkink (2005) are trying to illustrate some fundamental issues of cognitive science that to understand the nature of the word meaning. In any communication process, no communicator transfer the knowledge of any word to any communicant but only try to make the bridge of the real world knowledge of the communicant by the language utterance process. Therefore, no dictionary or the speaker transfer the world knowledge to listener, but only provides one or many synonyms of the text or word, till it match as exact to the word knowledge (Fig 1.1) of the communicator at a particular span of time or moment.

Fig No. 1.1: Word Knowledge discourse sphere

To describe the knowledge discourse of a word, we take eastern philosophers Rasa theory as the benchmark. It starts from Bhava (the emotion) itself. The listener/reader/consumer's Bhava at a particular time extracts the meaning or ultimate artistic joy of such words or texts in that time and sphere only.

As per the eastern philosophers like Bharatmuni, this poetic or performance joy of the text is Rasa and it comes out from the text's aesthetic value. It is the impression created on the mind of the consumer by the expressions of Bhavas (emotions) and it's experienced by it. Rasa's Foundation is laid upon a particular view of psychology that holds consumer's personality and according to which a few primary emotions live in the conscious and subconscious state of our being. These emotions are vast, amusing, pathetic, heroic, passionate, fearful, disgusting and wonderful. These emotions are running in a permanent manner within the text also. And here we may call it as dominant emotions or Sthai-bhavas.

However, the dominant emotions only can be tempted with the union of Vibhavas, Anubhavas and Vyabhikari-bhavas. Vi-bhavas are the situations which are responsible to bring out Sthai-bhavas and it has two aspects Alambana & Uddipana. Where the consumer or the pre-dominant mood of the person in whose mind Sthai-bhavas run is known as Alambana Vibhavas. And The environmental situation in that particular time like moonlit, spring, soft breeze, fragrance of flowers are Uddipana Vibhavas or the Stimuli.

Anu-bhavas are the effects seen after the emotions arise. They make reader or listener or spectator or the consumer of the text to feel or experience.

Vyabhikari-bhavas are the transitory and temporary mental states weakness, depression, anxiety, despair etc.. They strike mind and become the cause of experiencing a permanent mood.

In the atomic structure of word knowledge, the Vyabhikari-bhavas have no external presence but are moving within the Sthai-bhava just like the current flowing in a wire as soon as it comes in contact with the moods of the consumer, i.e. the Vibhava and Anubhava or the effects of the emotions. The Vibhava and Anubhava are the two external sphere belts of dominant emotions.

From this the consumer, the real primary word knowledge, the Anubhava (feel or experience) generates. This Experience factor within word knowledge is dynamic. As soon as the time changes, the experience of the Consumer of the word changes, so as to word knowledge.

However, the word knowledge only can be realized from the 'Upalabdhi' or the tranquil realization. This is the inner cream of experience contains the joy factor of the word knowledge. From here the tranquil joy only can be realized by the consumer. Here consumer means the entity that possessed the word at a particular time, i.e. at the time of speaking the speaker itself the consumer, where as the as soon as it reaches to listener, the listener is the consumer of the word knowledge. Till the realization, the 'Anand' factor or the Joy of realization of word knowledge is not being expressed. Here we may consider, the

The Tranquil-Joy's inner sphere is Aesthetics. It is the experience of appreciation. This aesthetic value of word knowledge can be realized in five degrees as (a) Udattha (Sublime), (b) Bhavya (Grand/Magnificent), (c) Sundara (Beautiful), (d) Labanya (Grace) and (e) Lalita (Fine/delectable). (Oxford Lectures on Poetry-A.C. Bradley) If we consider any famous object

beauties as the degree of sublime, then the beauty of Grate Himalayas will be Magnificent and the aesthetic value of a young girl in this degree is Beautiful. The internal aesthetic value within a baby or the childhood of Lord Krishna is the Grace form of Aesthetics. Whereas the fine or delectable beauty only can be expressed in joint form of Radha-Krishna, as the ultimate and highest form of aesthetics. Aesthetics focuses on the one or the other varies with the time and situation. Therefore time is the ultimate sphere of the Aesthetics in our word-knowledge diagram. And as the value of Aesthetics is the Love, therefore the Love remains within the Aesthetics as in subtle and spiritual form. With respect to time as the value of aesthetics, the love, the real word knowledge changes, the whole word-knowledge changes.

And here is the 'Radha', the ultimate form of divine love, the nearest synonymous of Knowledge and Aesthetics is attached to time, or the real word knowledge and it is speeded over the universe as human imagination reach or its beyond. The whole sphere of Knowledge is 'Radha'. As time changes, the world knowledge's internal value the divine or eternal love transforms to different form as the words and expanded to every sphere of Universe, or the human consciousness. Therefore the word or Sabda is Brhama, the omnipresent.

4. The term, Radha' as Myth:

Who is Radha? Is she the daughter of Vrishbhanu and Kirti? Is she Vrindavaneshwari? Is she Shri Krishna's first chief consort or if any? The unsolved discourse, is still hammering different philosophers and spiritualist as the before. To continue with the literary history of Radha, We can trace her from the Sanskrit work G?tagovinda (composed in 12th-century by court poet Jayadeva); the songs of the Maithil? poet Vidyapati (14th-century), the Bhakti poets Rupa Goswami (1489-1564) and Surdas (1478-1581) and from the Riti poets of different languages of India.

Radha, who devoted her whole life to Ultimate, the Parama-Purusha, but has achieved only the reproach; She is trying to buy the interiority in terms of affection, but had got only the snub; has tried to receive the love in terms of love, but gains only the cheating, exception and damn. However, still Radha alive, in Puran, in folktales and in public narration. Radha said in his own identity, "I have all the rights to receive entire the affection as the daughter of Brushavanu I am solitary follower of Chandrasena as the wife. However, Mother...that fortune has not comes to me at any time." Notwithstanding, I am filled with unthinking storm; I have converted myself as the insurgent to the situation. Because I am not 'Radha' but 'Dhara', the path; the path of Divine loves, the path of transforming human consciousness to divine consciousness with all eternal and pure love. Its movement is from time of Veda to Post-Vedic period, an independent entity. In Indian literary treasure, in the fantasy of age of Puran, sometimes she has becomes human to divine or has becomes divine to human; or has sometime she becomes ladies from lord.

As per the combine effort of Brhma Baibarta Purana, Padmapurana, Bayu Purana, baraha Purana, Matshya Purana and Markandeya Purana, Radha is daughter of Brushabhanu. Her birth is at Rayal Palace, her nurture is in rayal Majesty, and her life movement is in different social responsibility. However two Hindu mythological books Mahabharata and Bhagavad are in totally silent about Radha. In Baishnavism sentiment, Radha is the soul of Krishna, the Paraprakruti (Trans-nature). Therefore, Radha is the Psyche-daughter of Mythologist; is a beautiful questionnaire in the pages of Purana; is an endless source of divine joy. She is not only an expression of Feminism, nor is she Manwasini but Tapashwini. The love of Radha towards Krishna is beyond and a supreme higher order than the language of Byron to Korolin that, "My God, You shall pay for this, I'll wring that obstinate little heart". Therefore Radha and tranquil divine love are the synonymous to each other.

Again the identity of Krishna is not complete without Radha. So here is the crossroad. Does Radha, the supplement of Krishna or the complement of Krishna, or beginning of Krishna, or both are two sides of a coin inseparable from one another? Who is the beginning and where is the end? Are both Krishna and Radha are the form of human consciousness moving one to other intermingle and inseparably? To solve the above question we are trying to draw the discourse of 'Radha' considering 'Krishna' as an hypothesis or the primary form of human consciousness.

To define Radha, we have to understand the term, 'Love' as Radha is the supreme and divine consort of Krishna.

5. Love & Stages of love:

Love is the state of attraction but more than simple sensation, more than sense perception. "Love is that state of the heart, when both happy and sad both feelings are equal and the heart feels relaxed." Falling in love is nature's trick to get humans to pick the desires. It feels so wonderful because we are awash in hormones such as dopamine, oxytocin, serotonin, testosterone, and estrogen. Falling in love also feels great because we project all our hopes and dreams on our lover. However how it starts and what is relationship with language, where the place of love with the language pulls us to further introspects the issue. In the Word-Knowledge sphere, the subtle presence of love within the ring of Aesthetics tries to make a relationship with the other words so as to form sentence, the primary form of the language for communication.

There are very different types of love in the world. The way the individual love its romantic partner has nothing to do with the way he/she love his/her mother. Again loving a animal or attract towards a flower, liking a new dress are so different from the previous. Mental desire leads only to the purification of the natural love, but not the transformation of the soul. The longings of the soul come from the realization that this Love is available and waiting, and that the soul must become active and earnest in its endeavor to receive this Love and be transformed. The tranquil love within the human consciousness starts from attraction the primary stage of

love which we say as Krishna and ends at dedication, the highest form of love of human consciousness i.e. as we describe as Radha.

From the starting point of love i.e. attraction or Krishna, as soon as the human consciousness enters to higher dimension, the stages of love changes and ends at the Radha at last or the ultimate. To describe this we try to divide the stages of human consciousness in nine forms as below to define different form and stages of love with time and context. These are: (1) Attraction (आकर्षण), (2) Affection (अनुराग), (3) Friendship (सनेह), (4) Love (प्रेम), (5) Amour (प्रणय), (6) Mothering (ममता), (7) Devotion (भक्ति/ऋषि), (8) Surrender (समर्पण/गोपी), (9) Dedicated (समर्पित/राधा).

If seeing or touching somebody; hearing or speaking with somebody, touches your heart, then it is called affection. This is the second stage of love. Then the stage of friendship or liking comes out towards a worldly object. What we generally say the love of young couple may be treated as the fourth stage and the named as Love. And from here the love becomes more subtle and internal and spiritual till end to higher form of consciousness, the stage where time and aesthetics have no separation.

6. Radha, the ultimate form of love and Time:

To draw the discourse of Radha we take the stages of love starting from Krishna or attraction to Dedication or Radha as in vertical bar where as the time remains in horizontal. In vertical bar the crossing point of love and time is Attraction. In the ancient Sastra it is written that, 'Karshati Akajshati iti Krishnaha (कर्षति आकर्षति इति कृष्णः।)', means everything that attracts is Krishna. Whatever, wealth, Power, position, God, Nature, and the happiness drawn from the above object are the form of Krishna. In human sublimity, the attraction is attached to time. As the desire changes, the attraction change; so the love transforms with respect to time and situation. The human consciousness sphere starting from attraction reached to the ultimate stage of Radha, the timeless stage. Here the Love Time discourse relationships diagram (Fig 1.2) where the Aesthetics expressed with respect to love and time.

Fig 1.2: Love, Time and Aesthetics relationship

The knowledge of the entity remains in the words of a language. As the word is the symbolic representation of knowledge with respect to time. Therefore, the term, 'Radha' is the ultimate stage of love and also the human consciousness. However, here the super myth, 'Radha' behaves as the instance catalyst to express the transfer of word knowledge to Time wave.

7. Relationship between Word Knowledge and Time Wave:

From the above discussion we it can be understand that, where -

T = Thought; CT= Thought of Communicant; RT= Receiver Thought; Time wave = Tw,
Word Knowledge= Wk

We can now say and understand that:

$$CT + RT = 0$$

$$\text{Or } CT = -RT$$

The sum of CT and RT is the total thought

When total thought powered by time wave (Tw) the complete Word Knowledge (Wk) generates.

$$\text{Therefore: } (CT+RT)Tw = Wk$$

And complete word knowledge with respect to time is becomes dynamic respect to communicator and receiver.

Conclusion:

The ultimate unit of language, 'Word' germinates from thought transfers to wave of time. As soon as the time changes, the Bibhava, Anubhava, Byavicharibhaba and the mode of attraction change including the beauty or aesthetics. Therefore, the word-knowledge also remains changes and it is dynamic with respect to thought boundary, i.e. with respect to goal, mood and thought direction. Therefore, Radha is the evolving factor of Consciousness from Attraction to Dedication with the factor of Time. And every word-knowledge always starts from a time, germinates from thought of communicator, transfers to receiver through communicant, and reaches to timeless period in human consciousness. And this is the stage of endless divine joy. As the consciousness rises, the word-knowledge become clearer, takes the Communicant from poetic-joy (Rasa) to end-less joy (Raasa). In the process of communication, the communicator tries to map his or her word-knowledge consciousness level to the Communicant's consciousness level. And the same when mapped with receivers thought boundary, the word knowledge is understood as better. Where the Human natural languages varieties disappear and transferred to Universal language. Every receiver receives or interprets the same knowledge as per their experience or the ultimate and tranquil realization. □□

Footnotes:

- 1 Georges bataille, 'Visions of Excess', Selected Writings, 1927-1939, the Solar Anus, p.5
- 2 Jena, Dr. Bairagicharan, 'Saundaryatatwa O Odia kabyare saundarya chetana', Odisha Book Store, p.63
- 3 Utara Ramacharita, Bhababhuti, edited. Dr. Shrinibash Mishra, 'Saundarya Tatva O Odia Kabyare Saundarya Chetana', Bairagi Charan Jena, Odisha Book Store, p.98

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